

THE ROLE OF MUSIC AND SONG LYRICS IN TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE SKILLS

Mokhinur Sotimboy kizi Rakhimberdieva

Student, Chirchik State Pedagogical University

makhinurrakhimberdiev@gmail.com

Scientific adviser: **Said-Fozilxon Akmalxonovich Akmalxonov**

Teacher, Chirchik State Pedagogical University

akmalxonovsaidfozil@gmail.com

s.akmalxonov@cspu.uz

Abstract: This article focuses on the importance of using music and song lyrics in teaching English. The article talks about the role of music and words in teaching English. It is explained how to learn English through various activities and how to improve English language skills through various games.

Keywords: Teaching English, interactive methods, the benefits of music and song lyrics, vocabulary, communication skills.

Аннотация: В этой статье основное внимание уделяется важности использования музыки и текстов песен в преподавание английского языка. В статье говорится о роли музыки и слова в обучении английскому языку. Объясняется, как изучать английский язык с помощью различных занятий и как улучшить навыки английского языка с помощью различных игр.

Ключевые слова: Преподавание английского языка, интерактивные методы, польза музыки и текстов песен, словарный запас, коммуникативные навыки,

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola ingliz tilini o’rgatishda musiqa va qo’shiq matnlaridan foydalanish muhimligiga bag’ishlangan. Maqolada ingliz tili darslarini o’qitishda musiqa va qo’shiq matnlarining roli asoslanadi. Darslarni turli mashg’ulotlar orqali o’rgatish, turli o’yinlar orqali ingliz tili ko’nikmalarini oshirish haqida yoritib berilgan.

Kalit soʻzlar: Ingliz tilini oʻqitish, interfaol metodlar, musiqa va qoʻshiq matnlarining foydalari, lugat, muloqot qobilyati, tadqiqotchilarning fikrlari.

INTRODUCTION

The advancement of technology around the world is moving in the right direction. While studying, a significant number of pupils listen to music. The effectiveness of listening to songs while instruction is being given, as well as the enhancement of communication abilities. Because it has a lot of beneficial aspects, it soothes the activities in their brains, which in turn helps to enhance the mood of kids and contributes significantly to the improvement of their intelligence level. Aside from the fact that listening to music serves to motivate us, it also helps us learn new words and enhance our memory. Listening to music is a more fascinating, easier, and faster approach to learn English. One of the many advantages of listening to music is that it can improve one's speaking skills, listening skills, vocabulary, and pronunciation, among other potential benefits. The first step is to practice listening; the materials are genuine, which makes it easier to immerse oneself in the English world. Learning about culture, particularly the culture of the English language, will assist pupils become more interested in the subject matter. Not only can reading music texts help students expand their vocabulary, but music texts also contain a wide variety of idioms and phrases itself. By way of illustration, students listen to music that is based on lyrics, which allows them to acquire novel vocabulary and idioms. Later on, pupils are able to comprehend the lyrics of a variety of songs without having to consult the text. It is then that they repeat each day based on the text. To put it another way, the words of songs are also a terrific tool for improving pronunciation. By way of illustration, students who are learning English can improve their pronunciation by repeating the lyrics of English music or films. The lyrics contain a number of difficult words and phrases; by learning and committing these words to memory, pupils can further develop their writing and speaking abilities. It is beneficial and helpful for pupils to learn language through music and lyrics, which can help reduce stress that they experience. When we are learning a language, we

make use of a wide range of resources. For instance, we can study through books, social networks, as well as various channels on YouTube, Ibrat school, and Duolingo games. The sources that we use must be dependable and helpful. You Tube is among the most dependable channels among all of them. There are video lessons that can be found on the channel on YouTube. Other ways for them to learn English include watching videos on YouTube and repeating the text that they see. There are videos on YouTube that teach young children through the use of action games; therefore, certain videos and films are suitable for older students since they are suited for their level. Through the use of video tutorials, students can acquire knowledge. In addition, students can benefit from Ibrat Academy, and the Duolingo game is an excellent resource for students who are interested in learning through a range of games that are both entertaining and engaging.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Music in the classroom has the potential to not only increase student enthusiasm but also to create an atmosphere that is friendly. Students can improve their pronunciation, vocabulary, and fluency by using songs as a medium to assist them improve their language skills. Using songs in the classroom is important for a number of reasons, one of which being that songs are among the most effective ways to teach a foreign language. Writing, listening, and speaking in a natural and harmonic manner are the four fundamental abilities that they are able to develop and integrate as a result of their participation in the language class. In addition, the use of music and song in the classroom is beneficial for a number of reasons, including the fact that it can enrich the lesson by giving a break from the routine, as well as boosting the level of engagement and interest that students have in the subject matter. Due to the fact that songs have been shown to be the most efficient method of teaching English vocabulary, I decided to focus on this subject. Due to the fact that students, particularly younger students, find songs to be enjoyable and enjoyable, songs have the potential to improve the motivation of pupils to learn. As a result of the fact that selecting the appropriate method to teach English vocabulary will also have an effect on the ease with which children are able to remember language, songs may be the

most appropriate medium for teaching English vocabulary. The process of teaching and learning is a complete and utter failure if the appropriate approach and media are not utilised. For this reason, the focus of this study is on the utilisation of song media in the instruction of English vocabulary, particularly at the student level.

CONCLUSION

It can be concluded that songs are an effective way of teaching English vocabulary easily. Using songs to teach English vocabulary in class can increase student learning motivation as indicated by the activeness of students while taking lessons and students getting easier to remember and increasing student vocabulary day by day. When singing the song together, the song must be repeated three times. Hence, the students start to remember the song, and the child will automatically remember the vocabulary in the song. Moreover the teacher still has to play an active role in reading the child’s mood so that it is easy to be invited to learn because it is very influential. Students in a good mood will be quickly invited to learn while singing together. A student in a good mood can also affect their friends because if a child is not in a good mood he will usually cause trouble and disturb his friends. The researcher provides suggestions for future researchers to examine more than one teacher to find more complete new data and findings as well as comparisons between teachers to improve vocabulary teaching strategies using songs to make them even better.

References:

1. Akmalxonov, S. A. (2023). The main problem of learning english as a foreign language. *Finland International Scientific Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities*, 11(4), 573-576.
2. Graham, Carolyn. (2006). *Creating Chants and Songs*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
3. Murphey, Tim. (1992). *Music & Song*. Oxford: University Press.
4. Akmalxonovich, A. S. F. (2022, December). THE NECESSITY OF USING DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING ENGLISH. In *Proceedings of*

International Conference on Modern Science and Scientific Studies (Vol. 1, No. 3, pp. 420-425).

5. Scrivener, Jim. (2005). *Learning Teaching: The Essential Guide to English Language Teaching*. 2nd ed. Oxford: Macmillan.

6. <https://www.britishcouncil.org/voices-magazine/how-use-songs-english-language-classroom>

7. <https://teachingenglishgames.com/teaching-english-through-songs/>